

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth System**

The results of deliverables D2.1 and D4.1 are added to BISICLES-NEMO

Milestone MS12

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Milestone report

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Cover sheet: Copernicus Sentinel-1 SAR (synthetic aperture radar) image from 12 February 2022 over Bear Ridge with white shades indicating the presence of icebergs and sea-ice (Kostov et al., 2026).

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1. Means of verification of the achievement of this milestone

This milestone details improvements to the NEMO ocean model, which is used to drive forecasts of ice sheet mass loss (contributing to sea-level rise) through the NEMO–BISICLES coupled system. In particular, the work considers improvements to the representation of icebergs in NEMO that have arisen through other work packages of the OCEAN ICE project. In deliverable D2.1 the project developed new iceberg model physics, and in deliverable D4.1 the project developed new estimations for the calving of icebergs from Antarctica. This milestone details the resulting improvements to NEMO, which are supported by an improved representation of the ocean and ice conditions surrounding Antarctica, as demonstrated by the figures in this report and in our two published papers (Olivé Abelló et al., 2025; Kostov et al., 2026).

2. Work performed and main achievements

The main achievements of this milestone are improvements to the NEMO ocean–sea-ice–iceberg model (Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean; Madec and the NEMO System Team, 2024; Marsh et al., 2015; Merino et al., 2016). These NEMO model developments were carried out in collaboration between UKRI-BAS and CNRS-IGE. Section 2.1 was led by CNRS-IGE. The work described in section 2.2.2. was led by YUKRI-BAS.

2.1 Realistic calving thickness of simulated icebergs to improve their spatial and temporal grounding and melting distribution

Our work (Olivé Abelló et al., 2025) has improved the distribution of iceberg thickness in the 1/4° NEMO Southern Ocean model configuration. In our new algorithms, the largest icebergs are initialised to be exactly as thick as the ice shelf from which they calve, and updated estimates for iceberg calving fluxes are used. This results in a broader simulated ice-thickness distribution, and we observe iceberg keels extending to 600 m below the surface. We furthermore impose a simple scheme for interaction with bathymetry: if an iceberg moves into a model grid cell where the bathymetry is shallower than its keel, it is sent back to its previous position and its velocity is reset to zero. This scheme allows us to qualitatively reproduce satellite observations of iceberg grounding and fast ice over the shallow ridges of the Amundsen Sea and other Southern Ocean shelf seas (Fig. 1).

If icebergs do not interact with bathymetry, their rate of melting over the Antarctic continental shelf is on average 630 Gt yr⁻¹. However, the simple grounding scheme yields a much higher melting rate at 800 Gt yr⁻¹ (Olivé Abelló et al., 2025). This additional freshwater from icebergs promotes sea ice growth, strengthens the ocean stratification, and suppresses deep convection. A fast-ice parametrisation (Lemieux et al., 2015; 2016) furthermore allows grounded icebergs to block the transport of sea ice and to generate dipoles in sea-ice concentration consistent with satellite observations (Olivé Abelló et al., 2025).

Fig. 1: Replicated from Figure 5 of Olivé Abelló et al., 2025. Probability of (a) iceberg occurrence from Mazur et al. (2017) inferred from Advanced Synthetic Aperture Radar (ASAR) images with an effective spatial resolution of 150 m and (b) grounded icebergs in the REF experiment, in the Amundsen Sea. While iceberg occurrences in Mazur et al. (2017) were calculated for all of 2011, we selected a single random steady-state year from the REF experiment for comparison, as a repeated-year forcing simulation adds no additional significance. The grey solid lines indicate bathymetry contours from the IBCSO database (Arndt et al., 2013), and the light blue shading represents Antarctic ice shelves. For a clearer comparison, only probabilities above 5% in Mazur et al. (2017) are shown.

2.2 Improved dynamics of iceberg grounding and ungrounding in NEMO

Floating icebergs occasionally encounter shallow bathymetry and scour into the seafloor sediment, a feature previously not represented in NEMO and the main highlight of this work. This model development effort was tested in an Amundsen Sea (Antarctica) regional configuration of NEMO with a focus on Bear Ridge (roughly aligned with 110°W in Fig. 1 above), where observations reveal multiple grounded icebergs with long residence times and a large number of iceberg scours (ploughmarks). However, the improved NEMO iceberg dynamics described below are relevant to other shelf seas around Antarctica, where iceberg grounding is commonly seen.

Multibeam-bathymetric data were collected by BAS collaborators on the eastern side of the Bear Ridge. This has enabled manual mapping of scours, which inform the improved representation of iceberg-bathymetry interactions in NEMO. Furthermore, in order to model the sediment resistance acting on grounded icebergs (Chari 1975), we have used representative values for saturated density and shear strength from Amundsen Sea sediment cores (Smith et al., 2011; Clark et al., 2024). We have also considered the interaction between iceberg keels and the solid ocean basement, whether it lies below the sediment layer or is absent in deformable sediment. In that case, we model the Coulomb solid-body friction experienced by icebergs along the ocean basement. We incorporate the updated iceberg dynamics and grounding algorithms within the pre-existing Lagrangian iceberg module in NEMO. We test the updated model in a regional Amundsen Sea configuration similar to the setup of Caillet et al. (2023).

We first explore the balance of forces acting on freely floating icebergs (see Fig. 2). We find an approximate three-way balance between atmospheric drag, ocean drag, and the Coriolis force with almost no net acceleration. The Coriolis force is, as expected, oriented to the left of iceberg motion in the Southern Hemisphere. In contrast, the wind stress and the smaller ocean pressure gradient force are generally oriented to the right of the iceberg trajectory at any instant. This implies that the dominant forces (except ocean drag) are nearly orthogonal to the direction of motion and do very little work on the freely floating large icebergs. Only ocean drag acts to decelerate icebergs.

We also consider the force balance of kinetically grounded icebergs, icebergs that are embedded in the sediment but still moving (Fig. 3). Unlike the case of freely floating icebergs, the ocean drag on grounded icebergs has no dominant prevailing orientation against the direction of motion, and the ocean pressure gradients are not orthogonal to the iceberg's velocity vector. Atmospheric drag tends to drive kinetically grounded icebergs forward, but this is opposed by a large dissipative sediment resistance force.

These new model developments to the iceberg scheme in the NEMO model are detailed in Kostov et al (2026) and are ready for use by a wide range of NEMO model users across Europe and worldwide, including in NEMO-BISICLES and the UK Earth System model.

Fig. 2: Replicated from Figure 6 of Kostov et al., 2026. Contributions of atmospheric drag (a), the oceanic pressure gradients (b), the Coriolis force (c), the ocean drag (d), the net acceleration (e), and the average of (a)–(d) across all

test icebergs and all timesteps **(f)** to the momentum budget of simulated freely floating THICK icebergs in the Amundsen Sea in the SHORT simulation. Directions are denoted as F (forward, along the iceberg's direction of motion), B (backwards, against the direction of motion), L (to the left of the direction of motion), and R (to the right). The full length of the radial bars indicates the probability density function of acceleration in a given direction. For each panel in **(a)–(e)**, the sum of all directions is 100 %, but the bars along some of the directions are relatively small. For each bar in panels **(a)–(e)**, the range of acceleration magnitudes is indicated by the colours, and the probability of each magnitude class is indicated by the radial distance. Colour sections in panels **(a)–(e)** indicate the frequency distribution of the accelerations in each magnitude class. Note that the radial axis is different between panels **(a)–(e)**, while the colour scale is common to panels **(a)–(e)**. Panel **(f)** has a separate legend and a different colour scheme.

Fig. 3: Replicated from Figure 12 of Kostov et al., 2026. As in Fig. 2 above, but for the case of the kinetic grounding of thick icebergs. The net term in panel (e) includes the first-order dissipative forces not shown in this figure. Occasionally, the orientation of the Coriolis force is not strictly to the left of the iceberg motion for numerical reasons: the force is calculated using the projected directions of future motion at each Runge–Kutta stage of the iceberg dynamics algorithm.

2.3 References

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2.4 Open Science

Two datasets in open access are underlying the work presented in this milestone:

- Yavor Kostov. (2025). Updates to the NEMO iceberg dynamics and grounding (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15484879>
- Yavor Kostov et al., Modelled dynamics of floating and grounded icebergs, with application to the Amundsen Sea. Mosaic of satellite images showing Copernicus Sentinel-1 SAR (Synthetic Aperture Radar) data. DOI <https://doi.org/10.5446/70447> PID <https://av.tib.eu/media/70447>

Peer-reviewed open-access publications: The following publications are linked to the work in this milestone and the deliverables.

- Kostov, Y., Holland, P. R., Hogan, K. A., Smith, J. A., Jourdain, N. C., Mathiot, P., Olivé Abelló, A., Fleming, A. H., and Meijers, A. J. S.: Modelled dynamics of floating and grounded icebergs, with application to the Amundsen Sea, *The Cryosphere*, 20, 135–169, <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-20-135-2026>, 2026
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